

Diplomatic Order: The Problem of Ritual Efficacy in International Relations

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In spite of its long history, ritual tends to be dismissed on the ground that it is merely an ornamental activity. This is known as the problem of ritual efficacy. This paper identifies and examines three important debates on ritual efficacy: expressive versus instrumental, doctrinal versus operational efficacy, and asserted and actual efficacy. I argue that these are less than satisfactory approaches to ritual efficacy in general, and in the diplomatic domain, in particular. Instead, the paper proposes a more adequate understanding of efficacy in terms of the mutual acceptance of, and accountability to the diplomatic order that is at stake in ritual. In contrast to previous approaches that sought to create a universal theory of efficacy, I develop a context-specific account of ritual efficacy. Further, while they were interested in establishing the appropriate logic of validation—internal or external—I argue that the evaluation of diplomatic rituals' efficacy depends primarily on the diplomat's ability to unlock, and act in accordance with the meaning lodged in the messages transmitted by rituals. I refer to this as "informative efficacy". The paper differentiates it from what it is closest to, that is, performative efficacy, and uses examples to probe its explanatory reach.

El ritual, a pesar de contar con un largo historial, tiende a ser desestimado con la excusa de que es meramente una actividad ornamental. A esto se lo conoce como el problema de la eficacia del ritual. Este artículo identifica y analiza tres debates importantes relativos a la eficacia del ritual: eficacia expresiva frente a eficacia instrumental, eficacia doctrinal frente a eficacia operativa, y eficacia alegada frente a eficacia real. Argumentamos que estos enfoques no resultan satisfactorios, ni en lo referente a la eficacia del ritual, en general, ni en el ámbito diplomático, en particular. En cambio, el artículo propone una comprensión más adecuada de la eficacia en términos de la aceptación mutua y de la responsabilidad frente al orden diplomático que está en juego en el ritual. Desarrollamos, en contraste con enfoques anteriores que buscaban crear una teoría universal de la eficacia, una explicación específica del contexto de la eficacia del ritual. Además, argumentamos que, aunque aquellos enfoques estaban interesados en establecer la lógica adecuada de la validación (interna o externa), la evaluación de la eficacia de los rituales diplomáticos depende principalmente de la capacidad del diplomático para descifrar y actuar de acuerdo con el significado contenido en los mensajes transmitidos por los rituales. Denominamos a esto «eficacia informativa». El artículo diferencia la eficacia informativa con relación a aquello a lo que más se parece, es decir, la eficacia performativa, y utiliza ejemplos para estudiar su alcance explicativo.

En dépit de sa longue histoire, le rituel a tendance à ne pas être pris en considération, car il se résumerait à une simple activité d'ornement. Il s'agit du problème de l'« efficacité rituelle ». Cet article identifie et examine trois débats importants sur l'efficacité rituelle : efficacité expressive ou instrumentale, doctrinale ou opérationnelle, prétendue ou réelle. J'affirme que ces approches sont loin d'être satisfaisantes pour l'efficacité rituelle de façon générale, et dans le domaine diplomatique en particulier. L'article propose quant à lui une compréhension plus adéquate de l'efficacité par rapport à l'acceptation mutuelle de l'ordre diplomatique en jeu dans le rituel et aux comptes à lui rendre. Par opposition aux approches antérieures qui visaient à créer une théorie universelle de l'efficacité, j'élabore une représentation contextuelle de l'efficacité rituelle. En outre, alors qu'elles cherchaient à définir une logique de validation adéquate (interne ou externe), j'affirme que l'évaluation de l'efficacité des rituels diplomatiques dépend en premier lieu de la capacité du diplomate à discerner le sens des messages transmis par les rituels et à agir en conséquence. C'est ce que j'appelle l'« efficacité informative ». L'article établit une distinction entre celle-ci et ce qui s'en rapproche le plus, c'est-à-dire, l'efficacité performative, et utilise des exemples pour sonder sa portée explicative.

Introduction

Ritual activity consumes energy, resources and time. In principle, the pervasiveness of ritual and the constituent values it enshrines should indicate that ritual accomplishes something worth the exertion. But scholars and practitioners struggle to demonstrate what, if anything, ritual effectuates. Several issues are yet to be settled, including the nature and levels of such efficacy, its object (i.e., what is transformed *in* or *by* rituals), and the appropriate terms to use so as to characterize it. Further, scholars inquire whether efficacy exhibits distinctive features when it applies to rituals. Finally, for those who engage in, and for those who spurn ritual activities, the key for embracing either position rests, primarily, with the answer one provides to the question of ritual efficacy.

The question of ritual efficacy is bedeviling mostly because two hide in one. First, it is difficult to draw a wedge between ritual function and ritual effects (Durkheim 1965; Kincaid 1990). To make things worse, functions and effects, although in large measure related, tend to be treated as substitutable terms. In doing so, however, the two are not being confused; they are being conflated (Churchland 2005). Thus, questions about why people engage in ritual, and what effects can be attributed to ritual activities, are stripped of their distinctiveness. Moreover, a ritual can outlive deviations from its original function or serve opposite functions, which challenges a linear connection between the effectiveness of a ritual and its functional adequacy. Second, there is in any discussion about ritual efficacy, a concern with ritual failure without which efficacy would be less relevant, or even moot. Since this is the case, discussions of rit-

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ual efficacy lead naturally to ritual's failures (Koschut 2023, 290–307).

In ritual studies, discussions about efficacy have generally been shaped by two characteristics. First, concerns about efficacy occurred with reference to religious and cultural practices. What worked in this domain was assumed to work elsewhere. Second, efficacy was thought either in physical (instrumental) perspectives or in symbolic (expressive) terms. That also meant that the logic for evaluating ritual efficacy was either endogenous (from the performers' point of view) or exogenous (i.e., vetted by practitioners). However, this begs the question: "who, participant, or observer, is to decide whether procedures fail?" (Grimes 1990, 209,207). Indeed, practitioners and scholars tend to use different optics to evaluate what ritual accomplishes. Their readings are not only contrasting; they are sometimes contradictory. It is plausible to believe that disagreements between these two is one basis of our uncertainties about ritual efficacy.

This paper makes explicit ambiguities wrapping considerations of ritual efficacy, by opening up the concept to its different interpretations and offering an alternative approach to ritual efficacy. I am skeptical of attempts to design a theory of efficacy that captures the dynamism of all kinds of rituals, everywhere. As Apache put it, "wisdom sits in places." The efficacy of ritual varies. Analytically, it can be of many scopes and levels (Basso 1996). This, of course, is not the end of the argument but its premise. Indeed, the burden of our argument is that different rituals might call for different metrics for gauging their efficacy (Quack 2010, 185). Therefore, this paper puts forward a framework that enables us to understand ritual's efficacy in the diplomatic domain.

Each ritual fits into a domain in terms of which it makes sense. The diplomatic domain differs from the religious, on at least three counts. First, the operation of diplomatic rituals does not depend on gods' intervention which, in religious ritual, facilitates or is held to cause an outcome. Second, and relatedly, the efficacy of diplomatic rituals is intrinsic to their performance. Third, whereas religious rituals are understood in terms of "underlying ideas, emotions, structures, or relations that it represents" (Sax 2010, 5–6), diplomatic rituals rest on the complementary relation between the latter and rituals' communicative intent.

In this paper I argue, therefore, that the efficacy of diplomatic ritual is derivative of its informative capacity. The notion "informative" here brings two broad meanings in its wake. First, it denotes the activity of transmitting information. As Maria Mälksoo puts it, the effectiveness of rituals of military exercises and war games rests on the ability to "communicat[e] a deterrent intent" (Mälksoo 2021, 62). Second, informative refers to the process of both informing and shaping—to give form or to arrange a substance (Tambiah 1985, 143; Kapferer 1983, 193). That is, by encoding ritual contents in more or less invariant sequences, ritual form goes, then, beyond mere framing (to use a Goffmanian word) towards affecting what ritual constituents are in and of themselves (Solomon 2023, 581). We approach here what I understand to be the fundamental link between form and meaning. Diplomatic rituals are distinctive semiotic frames for translating (not only transmitting) information ("sign") into meaningful and consequential acts.

The upshot of this argument is that some rituals are the vehicle for representing ideas, but do not communicate anything. In John Searle's words, "one can intend to mean something, which is to represent an idea, without intending to communicate, which is to produce beliefs in an

audience" (Searle 1983, 78; Ringmar 2012, 7–8). In diplomatic rituals, meaning and effects, although distinguishable are not separate. In addition to transmitting conventional messages, diplomatic rituals also convey self-referential messages. While the latter indicates and does something about the present (existential) state of the participants, the former enacts a commitment. That is, by performing a diplomatic ritual, diplomats accept and indicate to themselves that they subscribe to whatever is encoded in the canon of the diplomatic order. In Hedley Bull's words, "Diplomatists. . .are visible expressions of the existence of rules to which states and other entities in the international system pay some allegiance" (Bull 2002, 166). This is one of the decisive logical entailments of diplomatic rituals. Diplomats, by participating in rituals, become themselves part of the order they are bringing to life.

Behind such an argument lie two analytical concerns. On the one hand, the study of ritual efficacy is not context-invariant; that is, assessing ritual efficacy is not an abstract process. Rather, it only makes sense in a particular domain and with reference to a specific order, whose rules are scripted prior to the performance. On the other hand, a diplomatic ritual is efficacious to the degree that participants accept the diplomatic order they enact, and analysts can identify the object of such acceptance. The formal and public nature of diplomatic rituals enable analysts to validate the effects of rituals.

The argument takes the following course. Like many attempts to navigate a new territory without the help of an orthodox map, this paper begins by scouring the literature to single out and discuss the most influential contributions to the question of ritual efficacy. Thus, the first section emphasizes approaches for which efficacy is a primary—not secondary—feature of ritual action (Wittgenstein 1993, 115–55). I do not attempt an exhaustive literature review; rather I place the paper in relation to the main flows of ritual studies that deal with efficacy. This scholarship is organized around oppositional hierarchies, such as instrumental versus expressive, doctrinal versus operational, and asserted versus actual, efficacy. We examine their contribution through two criteria: (i) What sorts of work rituals do and (ii) how do we know? I argue that views of ritual efficacy are not context-invariant, and most scholars put high hopes in revealing what is universal to ritual efficacy. This quest is vain. We cannot evaluate an Aborigine bush tucker in the Australian northern territory as we would a state dinner held in honor of a foreign leader. In contrast, in section II, I make two moves. On the one hand, I suggest that we discuss and evaluate ritual efficacy in a specific domain. This allows us to acquire a reasonable method on how to weigh evidence of rituals' work in context (See Evans-Pritchard 1937, 349; Durkheim 1965, 50; Goffman 1974, 1–2). On the other hand, I argue that the assessment of what ritual accomplishes cannot dispense with the fact that it is an action whose main signature lies in its specific form. Following Roy Rappaport, therefore, I suggest that ritual effects are derivative of its formal character. These, Rappaport calls "logical entailments" (Rappaport 1999, 26). Using empirical vignettes, I show that the fitness of ritual entailments to account for ritual efficacy finds increasing support in studies that connect human biological processes and rituals.

Ritual Efficacy: Core Wagers

The very notion of "ritual efficacy" meets with contrasting reactions. Practitioners thrust their fate upon rituals in the belief that they change something, that is, they can be ontologi-

cally consequential. A variation of this view argues that ritual itself has no agency, but individuals can use it to effectuate changes on whatever upon which it is imposed or, at least, create an occasion within which such effects become possible (Baele and Balzacq 2022, 10–2). On these occasions, however, the efficacy of rituals is derivative of the power of other factors, including emotional stimuli, spirits or gods which enable or facilitate a specific effect to materialize. Skeptics, by contrast, argue against the grain of this view. Ritual category, they contend, applies to either purely adorning actions or irrational behaviors (Smith 1991; Asad 1993; Sax 2010, 8). Such a view permeates the following passages from Martin Hollis: “certain Yoruba tribesmen carry about with them boxes covered with cowrie shells, which they treat with special regard. ... The tribesmen believe that the boxes are their heads or souls and what they are doing in treating the boxes in reverent way is protecting their souls against witchcraft” (Hollis 1968, 231; Skinner 1969, 3–53). Ritual is primarily disqualified here as an action which has no rational basis. The oddness of the action appears as the criterion that enables Skinner and Hollis to situate an action into the ritual category. Some leaders, too, seem to endorse this ornamental understanding of ritual. Thus, asked about the importance of French-German conferences, Angela Merkel quipped, “this has to do, not with ritual, but rather with deep convictions” (Cited in Sax 2010, 6). It is assumed therefore that ritual has no effect whatsoever on the world (Shils and Young 1953; Lukes 1975). In ritual activity, says Frits Staal, the result doesn’t count (Staal 1990, 131; Radcliffe-Brown 1965, 160).

However, a growing track of research supports the existence of a ritual agency (see contributions in this forum). Rituals make for changes in the status of people (Aalberts and Stolk 2020; McConnell 2018), in the powers they can claim (Cornut 2018; Wegner 2021; Knotter 2020, Kustermans et al. 2022), in the nature of their interactions with the world (Baele and Balzacq 2022; Solomon 2023) and, even more profoundly, in how they construe their identity (Mitzen 2006; Steele 2008; Aalberts et al. 2020). This generative aspect of ritual is often called “enactment,” which refers to three capabilities: bringing about, putting into force or setting something in motion (Grimes 2014, 243). However, certain effects associated with rituals can only be sustained if we bracket alternative explanations. For example, when David Kertzer (1988) holds, following a fruitful Durkheimian tradition, that rituals trigger emotions, he overlooks the fact that emotions already present can act as catalysts for a given ritual. Thus, emotions appear as carriers of ritual’s messages and meanings. Put otherwise, ritual effects are often dependent upon other mechanisms. Deepak Nair, for example, links rituals of sociability to several effects in the production of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations’ (ASEAN) diplomacy, including community maintenance, the creation of social capital, learning and socializing, and the generation of a “backstage” in order to defuse tensions (Nair 2020, 200–1). However, it seems to me, the mechanism that produces these effects lies less in ritual itself than in “the practice designed to foster sociability (sport, music, food, etc.)” (Ibid., 211). Examining the engagement and performance of North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) enhanced forward presence, Mälksoo reaches the conclusion that ritual effects are generated by the practices and (military) exercises that sustain the Alliance’s enhanced forward presence. But the question remains whether similar, but non-ritualized practices and exercises could lead to identical effects? In other words, what, if any, allows rituals to bring about the effects attached to them? If a ritual ought to be performed for these things to be en-

acted, we need to discuss the grounds for the effectiveness requisite to ritual, that is, to specify its defining elements.

The remainder of this section focuses, therefore, upon salient approaches to ritual efficacy. Because IR scholarship on rituals in general, and on ritual effects in particular are still in their infancy, I turn for inspiration to research results in anthropology and social theory in order to develop a characterization of ritual efficacy that can be translated into IR terms. I identify three main wagers, the first of which singles out important points of distinction about the nature of ritual effect (Table 1). It presents an opposition between symbolic and instrumental efficacy. The second wager concerns the level of ritual efficacy. It features a distinction between doctrinal and operational efficacy. The third, which is a variation of the second, pits asserted against actual efficacy. One of my concerns with these approaches, however, is that the specificity (if any) of efficacy as it pertains to rituals, remains largely implicit. Thus, this section winds up by raising the following question: is ritual so specific as to warrant a distinctive approach to efficacy, that is, a perspective that is significantly different from that which allows us to appreciate the efficacy of other types of social actions?

Expressive and Instrumental Efficacy

It is one thing to claim that ritual is efficacious and quite another to provide metrics by which such claims must be ascertained. Some hold that no account of ritual efficacy can be sustainable unless it is instrumental. As Tom Driver put it, rituals are “primary instruments designed to change a situation” (Driver 1998, 201). Others declare that, when it comes to ritual, causality is unfit to probe ritual effect; rather, one should resort to the lenses of expressive or symbolic kinds of efficacy (see Boussaguet and Faucher 2024). The scholar most closely related to the instrumental reading is James Frazer, whereas Durkheim has shaped the symbolic approach to ritual work, and his influence is still felt today. In Frazer’s account, to start with, ritual is better conceived of as an aspect of magic, and the two words are often used together—hence, the notion “magical ritual.” Performers of magical rituals think that their action will decisively alter the course of nature. Magical rituals, this is to say, “are believed to influence the course of nature directly through physical sympathy or resemblance between the rite and the effects which is the intention of the rite to produce” (Frazer 1963, 411). This perspective leads to a conception of ritual efficacy that is binary; it either works or fails. Further, in Frazer’s view, if participants to a magical ritual claim that their action has the capacity to effect a transformation in the world, analysts can gauge performers’ assertions rather easily by checking whether the consequences of their actions can be attributed to the performance of a ritual. The effect is counted as evidence of that action precedence.

One of the perennial challenges of an instrumental view of ritual is that the basis of ritual’s agency is indeterminate—What, for example, in ritual, enables it to do what it is purported to accomplish? Further, is the outcome contingent upon ritual itself or what practitioners do with/within rituals? In other words, means-end reasoning limits the efficacy of rituals to predictable results, nothing else. However, studies of healing rituals tend to suggest that some formal acts might result in the well-being of the one for whose sake it was performed, which is different from claiming that the sick person has been transformed into a healthy one (Dinzelbacher 2010, 85–7). Yet, the link between the ritual and a specific outcome remains unclear, unless we admit that the relation is

contingent on operations that escape a physical connection between cause and effect.

The other, expressive or symbolic, view of ritual efficacy sits opposite the instrumental perspective. It considers the material efficacy irrelevant to ritual action. As George Homans remarked, “ritual actions do not produce practical result on the external world—that is one of the reasons we call them ritual” (Homans 1941, 172). Of greater interest, in approaches that treat material instrumentality as extraneous to rituals, is that many activities can include both instrumental and symbolic aspects, but the defining features of these two components do not intersect. Such a view is entertained by Edmund Leach. He argues that killing an animal can involve both a technical and a ritual dimension, though on some other instances, the action can be merely technical but, perhaps, never entirely ritualistic. Be that as it may, any ritual involves some technical ingredients (matter, energy, etc.), whereas most technical actions operate free of ritual influences. In Leach’s words, ritual “denotes those aspects of prescribed formal behavior which have no direct technological consequences” (Leach 1964, 607). In short, it is a “symbolic statement” (Leach 1954, 13).

That ritual is expressive or symbolic has a long pedigree in anthropology. Victor Turner, for example, considers “symbol [as] the smallest unit of ritual” (Turner 1967, 19). For Alfred Radcliffe-Brown, the expressive or symbolic element in ritual is what sets it apart from technical acts (Radcliffe-Brown 1952, 143). However, Durkheim was among the first to offer a systematic exploration of the efficacy of rituals through a symbolic lens. For him, ritual symbolizes the structures and processes constitutive of the life of a community. Thus, to understand what a community cares about, the study of ritual functions is fundamental. As Frazer suggested, Durkheim agreed that the function associated with ritual can be judged either right or wrong. But his insistence that the analyst can excavate the true reasons for ritual practice differentiates his characterization of ritual efficacy from Frazer’s for whom the analyst must ground her/his study of ritual’s functions on the practitioners’ justification. This is obviously not to say that practitioners’ account of ritual performance is always wrong, nor that their perspectives and that of analysts’ cannot converge, as it sometimes happens. It should not be imagined, moreover, that all effect following from ritual is apparent. It is simply to recognize that, on the one hand, performers’ assertions about why they ritualize must not be taken too literally as Robert K. Merton once cautioned, and, on the other hand, that the focus on the manifest functions of ritual confirms the practitioners’ view but confines ritual efficacy to its physical aspect (Merton 1968, 73–138).

Indeed, Durkheim’s formulation rests on a distinction between “apparent” and “real” efficacy: “The real function of a rite does not consist in the particular and definite effects which it seems to aim at. . . the real function of the cult is to awaken within the worshippers a certain soul. . . Thus the apparent efficacy will seem to change while the real efficacy remains invariable” (Durkheim 1965, 431). Nevertheless, apparent and real efficacy have the same logical form. Both deduce ritual’s efficacy from the authenticity of the functions achieved. This comes at a price. The authentication of ritual’s functions relies on subjective experiences, but eschews external validation.

Doctrinal and Operational Efficacy

According to Sally Moore, ritual achieves two kinds of effects, each with its distinctive plug to empirical evidence. In the first place, “doctrinal efficacy is provided by the expla-

nations a religion itself gives to how and why a ritual works. The explanation is within the religious system and is part of its internal logic.” And in the second place, “Results, success failure are part of the operational effects of a ritual” (Moore 1977, 12). That is, doctrinal effect refers to the self-description provided by the domain within which ritual occurs whereas operational efficacy reflects the outsider’s perspective. In this sense, the outcome and consequences of rituals fall beyond the purview of the doctrinal effect.

However, I wonder whether doctrinal and operational efficacy really exhibit two sorts of efficacy. The matter embodies several levels of intricacies. First, the reasons why ritual works (doctrine) and the consequences of ritual (operation) are two interdependent, but nonetheless distinct realm of explanation. Without the doctrinal aspect, ascertaining ritual efficacy would be abstract. The doctrinal aspect provides a limited set of ends in whose terms the effects can be assessed. Yet, it is in the operational manifestation that the doctrinal characteristic is carried out and enlivened. For participation in a ritual is not only indicative of the subscription to the ends privately sought but also opens itself to the public’s gaze. Second, the self-description of rituals, which doctrinal efficacy was meant to be concerned with, and the operational efficacy are articulated to each other and vetted through one another’s lens (and encoded in the performance of the ritual).

This question—whether ritual efficacy is internally or externally validated—continues to obsess ritual scholars of various theoretical hues. Recently, Johannes Quack and Paul Töbelmann have worked to rethink the explanation of ritual efficacy, by distinguishing “actual” from “asserted” efficacy. A ritual effect is said to be actual when its consequences depend neither upon performers’ nor observers’ perceptions and thoughts. This is close to the most common understanding of effect as a result of a clearly demarcated cause. In general, several potential effects are attached to the execution of a ritual. For example, in addition to changes in biological and emotional conditions (e.g., rise in blood pressure, excitement), a ceremony of initiation transforms the ontological status of the initiate from an alien to a brother or sister and grants the new member of the congregation deontic powers (rights and duties)—e.g., attend meetings of the congregation, participate in deliberations or vote. It will serve to remember that, for the effect to ensue, the procedure required by the ritual has to be properly executed. The matter is obviously easier when these are direct or expected consequences. But ritual activities presumably, can also produce indirect effects, that is, ends that are different from effects for which they were performed.

We come here to the realm of asserted efficacy. The first difference between actual and asserted efficacy is that, in the latter the link between ritual and its effect is not simply, or even at all, constitutive of the performance of the ritual itself but is dependent upon an external appraisal, either from the analyst or the practitioner. The second line of demarcation is that, asserted efficacy is established by relating particular effects to the “intentions, expectations and/or perceived functions of the ritual” (Quack and Töbelmann 2010, 7). This raises two problems, however. The first is that rituals effects do not always match the intention of those who perform them (Humphrey and Laidlow 1994, 98). A head of state intends to honor a newly accredited Ambassador by organizing a dinner on her behalf, but the dinner also reveals, most likely unwittingly, that the Ambassador’s country is just a junior partner. The second problem is that, researchers, performers and witnesses might hold different views about the intentions, expectations and perceived functions of a ritual. This leads us to an even more serious problem with the cate-

Table 1. Categories of Ritual Efficacy, Simplified

Categories	Sources of Efficacy	Forms of Validation	Logics of Validation
<i>Instrumental</i>	Technical Factors	Existence of a causal link between rituals and visible effects	External
<i>Expressive</i>	Symbolic Ingredients	Authenticity of the function achieved	Internal
<i>Doctrinal</i>	Rules of the relevant domain	Identification of the ends prescribed by the relevant domain	Internal
<i>Operational</i>	Ritual procedures	Operational manifestation	External
<i>Asserted</i>	Intentions, expectations, and functions of rituals	Relation between effects and intentions, expectations and (perceived) functions of rituals	Internal
<i>Actual</i>	Ritual means, whether symbolic or technical	Direct link between the execution of ritual and its purported consequences	External

gory of efficacy as such: Is there any hierarchy between these perspectives, and who ratifies it? To date, however, there is no rule to adjudicate such conflicts of interpretation (Stewart and Strathern 2014, 96). The uncertainty that is thus introduced turns out to have unsettling implications. Ritual efficacy entails a judgement about what should happen as a result of its performance. That is, establishing the efficacy of a ritual always calls on the perspectives of the agents involved, for the practitioners' accounts is as crucial to the notion of efficacy as is the analyst's. But the ends participants purport to accomplish in or by rituals must have neither a causal nor an aesthetic captivation for the analysts.

Ritual Form, Efficacy, and Diplomatic Order

The resort to classificatory strategies is easy to understand. It enables us to navigate if not manage the complexity of the issue of ritual efficacy, by slicing the question in separate categories. But classes of ritual efficacy are locked into dualistic clusters, each category claiming virtues that the other lacks. What should be a starting point turns into being an end in itself. In dualistic categorizations, differences overwhelm other alternatives, including the possibility of finding similarities or syntheses. We should therefore not overdraw distinction between, for instance, expressive and instrumental aspects of rituals, which diplomats do not make (Neumann 2012). To propose that diplomatic rituals involve, albeit in varying degrees, different classes of efficacy, is not to propose that changes wrought by instrumental and symbolic acts arise from similar processes. Instrumental efficacy depends on physical processes whereas symbolic acts effectuate whatever they accomplish, by meaningful processes. However, the path of physical efficacy I have in mind is not mapped upon the laws of physics. The efficacy of incantations is not that of bullets and bombs. It may be proposed, rather more specifically that, in the realm of rituals, physical processes refer to, first, chemical and neural signals, which are triggered by the information symbolically encoded and transmitted by the sender; second, this information is filtered by the receiver's senses and, third, dispatched to different parts of the body (Bateson 1972, 452). The argument is, in other words, that ritual efficacy depends on its informative capacity, which is relayed by constructed and learned meaningful symbolic repertoires and neural pathways that actualize physical processes (Campbell 1959; Erickson 1966; Bell 1992). Whenever diplomats perform a ritual, they both accept and embody the diplomatic order it enacts. They live the order in the formal postures and words of rituals.

The form of ritual, says Tambiah, is "the ordering and pattern of presentation of the ritual language, physical gestures, and manipulation of substance" (Tambiah 1985, 143). In other words, in ritual, acts and utterances are formalized. By "formalization," I mean, in the present context, first, that words and gestures constitutive of rituals are structured in a distinctive fashion, which allows us to set ritual apart from other types of social events or phenomena. Put in a slightly different way, ritual efficacy is said to be brought about by certain kinds of words, the form in which they are strung together and the rules in accordance with which they are so strung. This is a procedural view of formalization. Second, formalization refers to an articulated form, which activates an operative semiotic function, in the absence of which rituals would be inconsequential. As Rappaport puts it, "inasmuch as the substance of the ritual is infinitely various, this must mean that these meanings and effects follow from ritual's universal form" (Rappaport 1999, 27). In recognition of the function with which they are invested, I shall refer to this sort of formalization as a "semiotic"-oriented view of formalization. These two kinds of formalization sustain two approaches to formal efficacy. The difference between the two rests, it is the claim here, on the degree to which they subscribe to performative exigencies, how they assess ritual outcomes and identify deviations, torsions and failures whenever they occur.

I go on to trace analytically the connection between rituals and performativity, making the argument that performative or constitutive efficacy proceeds from a false premise. Identifying what the performative dimensions of ritual are, is one thing; reducing the whole ritual to performativity is, I show below, untenable. Moreover, the performative view of ritual efficacy overstates conventional effects and overlooks meaningful consequences of rituals. While providing the meaning that ritual conveys is not necessary for a ritual to be effective, such provision often increase its plausibility. As Michael Polanyi argues, "anything that functions effectively within an accredited context has meaning in that context" (Polanyi 1958, 58). Thus, what is key is the reciprocal orientation of effectiveness and meaningfulness that is expressed as acceptance, that is, a crucial logical entailment of diplomatic rituals.

Meaning and Performative Paths

Ask any former ambassador how the presentation of credentials works, and you will get more or less the following description:

On that day, the chief of protocol, wearing a morning coat or uniform, goes to his embassy and solemnly calls on him and his main collaborators, then takes them to the palace of the head of state in large black cars used for such ceremonies.... After the national anthem has been played the ambassador steps forward, presents his credentials to the head of state and gives his ceremonial speech, in which he evokes the “traditional bonds of friendship” uniting the two countries, highlighting his desire during his mission, “to see them grow closer and further develop.” The head of state responds courteously After the traditional glass of champagne, the head of state and the ambassador engage in casual conversation in which each one tries to make out the other’s true intentions... (Chambon 1983, 95).

There are three points to be made here. First, the conventional and fixed aspects of the procedure ensure that things are carried out in an orderly and predictable manner. Second, the invariant features of the event itself are operative, that is, they affect events and behaviors themselves. In this light, behaviors and words not only express the ritual, but they are also entailments of its punctilious sequences. There are of course opportunities for diplomats to innovate, but their creativity does not affect the outcome of the event and remains subservient to the prescribed aspects of the presentation of credentials. Further, when agents innovate, they often do so within the parameters set by the ritual they enact. For if they were to cut a new ritual from whole cloth, participants would likely be disoriented, and the new ritual might not be recognized by many of them as such. In short, any given ritual allows variations, but within formally constrained patterns (Cornut 2018, 721). Seen thus, ritual efficacy involves both fitness of the procedure and achievements (entailments).

A key concern arises: do ritual achievements necessarily follow from the fitness of the procedure? Yes, as broached by Stanley Tambiah, in that rituals are acts “of the ‘illocutionary’ or ‘performatives’ sort, which simply by virtue of being enacted (under the appropriate conditions) achieve a change of state or do something effective” (Ahern 1979; Tambiah 1985, 79, 1–17; Austin 1962). Efficacy is procedurally determined. And no, says Rappaport: ritual, to the degree that it imposes specific meaning on words and gestures, relies on semiotic indices in order to accomplish its effects. Further, performativity “has nothing to do with signification” (Deleuze and Guattari 1988, 5). In other words, the relation between ritual and performativity is less straightforward than Tambiah assumed. Thus, the theoretical discourse on which the reduction of ritual to performativity relies is in need of a fairly fundamental reorientation. That would require, on the one hand, some efforts in specifying the interpretation and role of performativity in ritual, that make discussions about efficacy possible in the first place. Second, I argue that there is an alternative way to think about performativity that does not reduce it to conventional rules or elevates efficacy to an inherent feature of ritual. This proposal turns out to be directly connected with the fact that ritual efficacy can be ascertained, I argue, only by the acceptance of participants who express their adherence to an interaction order by completing a ritual.

According to Tambiah, performativity is thought to compensate for the flaws of the instrumental view of ritual efficacy, for if the scholars keep “seeing... rites as acts launched by the actors to achieve practical results by suspending the laws of motion and force as we understand these laws in modern physics, then obviously such acts as must be declared false” (Tambiah 1985, 136). In contrast, the explanatory net of performative efficacy enables the analyst to rescue rituals from the stigma of being construed as irrational practices. Thus, Tambiah argues, “rites are conventional acts

which should be examined within a performative frame. [This] opens a new horizon for viewing the logic of such purposive acts and the canons for the validity from the actors’ point of view” (Ibid.). But to understand efficacy in performative terms reinstates the separation between the analysts and practitioners, as solely the latter are custodians of the validity of ritual efficacy. Implicitly, this also means that, for Tambiah, the observer’s approach to ritual tends to emphasize the “technical-causal” effects of ritual, that is, its perlocutionary consequences. Concerning the significance of such a distinction, Tambiah writes: “there are also constitutive act, which, although they realize their performative dimension, may yet be uncertain of realizing their expected perlocutionary effects. A classic example is curing rituals. . . , which, though performatively valid, may or may not induce cure in the patient” (Ibid., 135, 79). In other words, unlike the illocutionary acts, the perlocutionary acts are not fixed, that is, not constituted by the production of conventional utterances in specific circumstances.

A procedural-oriented (performative) conception of ritual efficacy raises five problems. First, it deafens us to the possibility that a ritual performed incorrectly can still nonetheless be regarded as efficacious by its practitioners (Hüsken 2007a, 351–52). Second, ritual performers sometimes recognize a new effect—that is, an effect out of the scope of a ritual—as part of what a given ritual can do (Grimes 2011, 1–34). Third, a great deal of rituals purport to enact a state of affairs that cannot be reduced to performative conventions. Fourth, ritual practitioners often or usually perform rituals of exculpation to either fix or avert the negative consequences arising from a procedure gone awry. This reveals that risks are integral features of rituals, which forces us to ask: how serious a procedural deviation must be for a ritual to be ineffective? (Hüsken 2007a, 23). Fifth, performativity may “explain at least part of what is hidden in Hubert and Mauss’s ‘efficacy *sui generis*’. . . [Ritual] is efficacious not only in the sense of a local confidence that it works, but it does in fact work, and all it needs in order to work is the local agreement that this is the way to do it” (Emphasis in the original. Sorensen 2006, 526). The constitutional transition from one state to another effected by ritual occurs only if the performance of the procedure of the correct type sets appropriate conditions for the transition (Gardiner 1983, 348). However, in this light, performativity is at one and the same time the means and the end of rituals. Put simply, conventional effects are achieved by conventions. It follows that ritual effectuates the state of affairs with which it is concerned. In short, efficacy is unavoidable.

I propose two ways out of this conundrum. One clarifies the relation between performativity and rituals. The other reinterprets the relation between perlocution and illocutionary acts. First, instead of characterizing the whole of ritual in performative terms, I argue that some sequences of ritual acts host performative properties. But it seems quite contrived to suggest that rituals *are* performatives. Indeed, not all performatives are rituals and there is more to rituals than performativity. At the same time, the “formal characteristics of ritual enhance the chances of success of the performatives they include” (Rappaport 1999, 115). Second, in so far as illocutionary and perlocutionary acts are woven into ritual sequences, the relation between the two is recalibrated. The rules for performativity in the ritual stipulate what the action “can be” and the formality of ritual embodies what the point of the action is (Humphrey and Laidlow 1994, 96).

A caveat needs to be entered here. Saying that actors follow a script should not be interpreted as participants forsake any authorship. First, they are indeed those who act, though they are ritually committed. Second, and perhaps more impor-

tantly, rituals depend upon the work of practitioners who demarcate rituals from the everyday flow of actions, primarily by abiding by the rules of a stipulated kind of action. This is to say that diplomatic ritual warrants a momentary suspension of the ordinary and signals the emergence of the extraordinary in the course of the ordinary. For rituals disrupt to the extent that they are able to preserve their internal pattern, which sets them apart from non-ritual activities. As Steven Lukes' puts it, rituals are "rule-governed activity of symbolic character which draws the attention of its participants to objects of thought and feeling. . . they hold to be of special significance" (Lukes 1975, 291). This helps understand—if in part—why Catherine Bell resorts to the concept of "ritualization" in order to emphasize the process by which the differentiation between ritualized and non-ritualized action takes shape (Bell 1992). This observation provides ground for arguing that when agents enact a ritual, they adhere to a form, which is not entirely of their own making. By doing so, they deflect their intentional sovereignty, as far as the acts which compose the ritual are concerned. In short, ritual participants are both and are not authors of their acts. Participants have a rather precise idea of what is expected from them when they embark on ritual proceedings. As a consequence, "the perlocutionary force inhering in the formality of rituals supports whatever performatives are enacted in ritual" (Rappaport 1999, 118).

In sum, ritual efficacy can be evaluated from the point of view of its procedure or from the point of view of the sequels, the terminal feelings, beliefs, thoughts and actions that are subsequent to or contingent upon it. While the procedure is governed by rules and conventions, the resulting state of affairs is not, at least not necessarily. In addition, it is not unusual that participants would alter the procedure if slightly to augment ritual's efficacy. It is important to note, however, that such procedural alterations can occur unconsciously. Either way, the outcome is not derailed. Finally, a broken off ritual or a disrupted procedure, may but need not immediately render the ritual impotent.

For a better understanding of what is at stake, I shall discuss an example here. The Assyrian King Esarhaddon's attempted in 669 BC to return the statue of the deity Marduk and his wife Zarpanitu to where it was captured two decades previously (Babylon) by his father. This was a diplomatic act of reconciliation and peacemaking. But when the convoy arrived at the border, Marduk made an oracular utterance through the mouth of a servant that the procession had to be called off. The return of Marduk and his wife was interrupted. Esarhaddon passed away a year later and could not enjoy the benefit of his reconciliatory policy. But his son and heir, Assurbanipal, finally managed to return Marduk and Zarpanitu to Babylon, and accordingly completed the procession (Ambos 2007, 31–4).

Today, most diplomatic rituals are immune from the putatively direct intervention of the gods, and their effects do not belong to the occult. But the main lessons of this example lie elsewhere. It reveals, indeed, that ritual conveys messages that are not only allo-communicative (speaking to others) but also auto-communicative (speaking to oneself). That is, ritual is an "outer framework which both occasions and identifies an inner event" (Murdoch 1970, 16). It communicates something about the participants as well as about the diplomatic state of affairs the body of participants contributes to. Further, meaningful acts are the vehicle of ritual's conventional effects. In bringing together the meaningful and the conventional, and recognizing that ritual can be allo-communicative and auto-communicative, I am, among other things, drawing attention to the fundamental distinction between what

is encoded in the invariant form of rituals and the significance of transmitting messages through and within ritual's invariant form, to those who are thereby enlisted in—not only passively targeted by—ritual performance. In Searle's words, "when one enters an institutional activity by invoking the rules of that institution one necessarily commits oneself to such and such ways, regardless of whether one approves or disapproves of the institution" (Searle 1969, 189). These observations provide grounds for taking diplomatic ritual's efficacy to be dependent upon as well as resulting from performers' acceptance of the diplomatic order.

Take handshake, one of the most common gestures of the diplomatic ecosystem. Iconic cases provide us with well-established examples of handshakes that have left a mark on diplomatic history (e.g., Raul Castro and Barack Obama–2013; Yasser Arafat and Yitzhak Rabin sealing the Oslo Accords–1993; and the one between Mikhail Gorbachev and Ronald Reagan, in 1988). In diplomacy, one talks of handwork to indicate that handshakes follow a precise code. There are highly detailed rules about the "ideal" handshake; it should be brief but not evasive, nor too long, which would be tantamount to taking the other person's hand hostage; it must convey force without being domineering, be warm but not invasive (Post 1940, 23). Handshakes are both a ritual of transition and of access, in Goffman's sense (Goffman 1967, 80). Indeed, a handshake signals the beginning or end of an interaction or diplomatic situation. Those shaking hands acknowledge one another and thereby "confirm that they consider one another to be civil individuals, paying quiet tribute to the person's sacred nature" (Keck 2012, 486). Shaking hands constitutes an acceptance of the diplomatic order as much as it reinforces the conventions in accordance with which diplomatic interactions are supposed to operate.

One might object on the grounds that handshakes are less central here than they appear. But our reading is confirmed by recent studies in the neurosciences. The work of Sandra Dolcos et al. on the interpersonal and emotional effects of handshakes proves that shaking an interlocutor's hand does indeed have a decisive impact on social interactions, both before and after (Dolcos et al. 2012, 2292–305). Before the interaction, a handshake tends to improve the impression one has of the person and to reduce the negative effects of bad impressions. Likewise, a well-executed handshake is a good way of galvanizing those involved and mitigating the potential negative effects from malfunctions in interactions. As Deborah Schiffrin argues, the smooth completion of a handshake stands as "the implicit assurance that the interactions to follow will be similarly coordinated" (Schiffrin 1998, 191). For a handshake is an essential, constitutive unit of the meaning attributed to the situation in which it occurs (Balzacq 2019, 117–8). Likewise, Dolcos et al. argue that a handshake helps create a framework for predictable interactions, without which mutual trust is unimaginable. The mechanism underlying these effects of handshaking is located in the nucleus accumbens, a neuronal network in the basal forebrain, deeply involved in laughter, dependence and addiction, and in the reward system. Greater activity of the nucleus accumbens can be seen in an individual shaking hands than in one avoiding doing so, or using other means of opening or closing an interactional sequence. Simply put, handshaking is thought to have a positive effect on those doing it. All the channels and consequences of handshaking, often treated off-handedly, have yet to be enumerated. But the results from neurosciences indicate that it is far from being a mere decorative feature of diplomatic interactions.

We know it but we sometimes forget; diplomatic order is pervasive and obdurate. It is not always, but often taken for granted. It is, however, particularly sensed when disruptions or skids occur. Such disruptions—always a prospect—can take various forms, ranging from awkward encounters to mutual hostility, through the incapacity to communicate or coordinate. Whenever a ritual is attacked or undergoes a deviation, it instigates debate. As a consequence, “when ritual properties are broken, the person who are present feel more uneasiness, ranging from mild humorous scorn to disgust to, in extreme cases, labelling violator mentally ill” (Collins 2005, 25). This is beginning to be well documented in diplomatic studies. For example, Simon Koschut’s account of ritual activities within NATO, shows that members of the alliance react wrathfully against outsiders and, even with a higher intensity, “renegade insiders,” who disrupt the ritual procedures which govern the sacred nature of their community life. In describing what happens, he asserts that “deliberate violations against these sacred elements resemble the breaking of a taboo and give rise to strong negative feelings” (Koschut 2023, 295). Ritual helps organizations such as NATO to protect themselves from harmful effects of deviant behaviors. But deviance contributes also, perhaps paradoxically, to preserving diplomatic order. Diplomats are joined together in social relations governed by a set of rituals which impart constancy and stability to diplomatic order. Ritual, that is to say, fulfils a boundary-making function for the diplomatic order since it is precisely by screening participants’ behaviors that agents select what belongs to within that order and insulate it from variations and deviant behaviors that belong outside it (Collins 2005, 48). One of the most interesting questions, although it falls beyond the scope of this paper, is how many variations a diplomatic order can tolerate or absorb before it loses its unique shape, its distinct relational configuration?

Let us return to handshakes. A handshake is a coordinated action—a movement toward the other that awaits a response, without which the situation becomes embarrassing. With an outstretched hand, one gives a part of oneself; in that sense, it is a form of “total prestation” (Mauss 2007, 10). A handshake appears as a gift. More than this, the outstretched hand, while inviting, obliges the recipient to accept and reciprocate. A handshake belongs to those activities where the core values of diplomacy are figuratively located. The performance of a handshake is one and the same time the undertaking of the obligation that is lodged in the diplomatic order. Thus, whenever a diplomatic encounter happens, the observer’s attention is normatively directed toward the handshake. In contrast, the absence of a handshake in a situation that ordinarily calls for one prompts comments about the quality of relations and the diplomatic order they contribute to.

This was the case with Donald Trump’s refusal to give the traditional handshake to the press during Angela Merkel’s visit in March 2017. In side-stepping that ritual, the two leaders immediately fueled much speculation. This example underscores two aspects of diplomatic rituals: the intercorporeality of ritual and the agency of actors involved therein, and these need to be teased apart. On the one hand, in diplomatic rituals, perhaps more than in most other ordinary encounters, the body is a “device that reveals” (Pile 2010, 11). That is, bodily copresence enables participants to scan and interpret each other’s signals (Fierke 2013, 22; Wong 2016). On the other hand, what observably goes on in the intentional disruption of what otherwise should lead to a shared rhythm, is that actors reclaim their agency (Cornut 2018; Solomon 2019). Viewed through the frame of diplomatic or-

der, such transgressions undermine the rules of civility and decency, which characterize diplomacy (Sofer 2007, 31–8; Mitzen 2015).

But another perspective prompts a degree of caution. For viewed through the logic of international hierarchies, Trump’s behavior might be read less as a lack of understanding of the assumptions as well as conventions that underpin diplomacy than a conscious unruly move for situational gains, which aims to reassert US supremacy—for is there a more potent expression of power than gaining from deliberately breaking rules? (Opondo 2010, 109–27). Finally, less commonly discussed, is the possibility that what one enures as ritual disruption is another’s need for self-continuity. That is, some agents make a career breaking and departing from rules and this sets them apart, to the extent that it defines who they are. Yet, the capacity to extract concessions from other parties by not playing by the book depends a great deal on the distribution of power in the international system. Moreover, as Fiona McConnell (2018) shows, pressures to follow ritual stipulations are higher on those whose status within the diplomatic world remains precarious. Nonetheless, even a powerful actor who consistently violates rituals that underpin a diplomatic order would be considered either as an amateur or a menace to that order. Taken together, these perspectives foreground ritual’s unavoidable “interpretive indeterminacy” (Lukes 1975, 297–300). The lesson we might draw from such analysis is not entirely settled. Be that as it may, when rituals are contested or not executed competently, different layers of interpretations are called for.

In truth, a handshake probably would not have dispelled the speculation about sour relations between the two leaders, but it may have helped redirect attention to other topics and provided a different way of framing the visit. Thus, contestation and infelicities become the source of diplomatic tensions precisely because it is ritual, “an identity-forming activity and means of reproducing a group’s values, social structures and habitual properties” (Langer et al. 2010, 121). In this respect, it is both the collective identity of agents and the anchor of their social order that are at stake when agents negate the rituals that provide and make visible what is essentially invisible: the basic fabric of their social bond. This means, in other words, that diplomatic rituals’ efficacy is not assessed by the latter ability to bring actors to comply with the obligations inherent in a given ritual; rather, it is efficacious if we can show that the obligation to shake hands is constitutive of the diplomatic order and doing otherwise trespasses against if not undermines it.

Coda: Diplomatic Order and Ritual Entailments

Fundamental to our conceptualization of ritual efficacy is the insight that efficacy is domain specific and that the efficacy of diplomatic rituals rests on the acceptance of a diplomatic order. The major problem of all previous approaches to ritual efficacy has thus been the habit to detach the assessment of ritual efficacy from the existence of a “sufficiently great common pool of cultural dispositions among all concerned” (Quack and Töbelmann 2010, 23). The term diplomatic order can be amplified to cover how the sequences of rituals that help participants to navigate the field of diplomacy, through oscillation of war and peace, are ordered. It can also, on occasion, refer to the corpora, commensurable processes, of a more or less coherent diplomatic tradition (e.g., the Chinese diplomatic order, the French diplomatic order). Here, diplomatic order denotes a pattern of regularities resulting from the common observance by diplomats of shared rules (not necessarily consciously), by which they govern their inter-

actions across settings. Because it is function of a “common understanding of a script or other protocol of interacting,” (Marsden 2015, 318) diplomatic order enables diplomats with vastly conflicting material interests, different cultural values and social backgrounds to take account of each other and develop an “intuitive feel for how their interactions should proceed,” and fend off divergent definitions of the situation (Crossley 2011, 179; Goffman 1967).

The primary function of diplomatic rituals is not to “control behavior directly, but rather to establish conventional understandings, rules and norms in accordance with which [diplomatic comportment] is *supposed* to proceed” (Rappaport 1999, 123). In this light, when diplomats ritualize, they do two things at once: they ascribe existence to a diplomatic order *and* accept it. That is, the act of acceptance is that which characterizes the efficacy of diplomatic rituals. For a logical entailment of the performance of diplomatic rituals is to substantiate the diplomatic order as “it *informs* them” (Ibid., 125). Diplomats do not only realize that order by following conventions, but they also repeatedly establish the conventions, rules, and norms in terms of which the effects of diplomatic rituals are accomplished. That is to say, rituals appear as a “meta-performative” (Ibid., 126).

It is obvious but nevertheless worth stressing that there is no diplomatic order without rituals—though this is an abstract possibility, no recorded historical evidence supports it (Cohen 2001; Lafont 2001). However, there is more to a diplomatic order than ritual. That is, in common parlance, ritual is a necessary—though not sufficient—condition for the generation and sustenance of a diplomatic order. Yet, the performance of ritual hatches a diplomatic order. The matter can be put simply: to perform a diplomatic ritual is necessarily to commit to a diplomatic order and to its logical expectations and consequences. It is to be stressed in all this that, the relation between a diplomatic order and ritual is not optional. Rather, they are inextricably entangled.

It is well to make explicit two assumptions tacit thus far. First, most rituals that animate diplomacy are encountered in different settings, either public or private. In fact, handshake, eating or large gatherings are not specific to diplomacy. While they share a unique ritual form regardless of the setting within which they occur, these rituals derive their specificity from the characteristics and arrangement of signs constitutive of the rituals that shape the diplomatic order. Second, the ability to interpret and understand signs conveyed by diplomatic rituals is cultivated, not a natural feature of diplomats. Obviously, there are great differences among individuals in their capacity to receive and to be affected by a ritual. The efficacy of diplomatic rituals, that is, their ability to form and transform that which they refer to, rests with the capacity of participants to receive the message they convey. The more formal the ritual, the more participants within a specific order require training to process the meaning transmitted. Thus, for diplomatic rituals to produce their effects, participants must be immersed in a common semiotic habitat. Indeed, participants are always participants within a distinctive ritual order, one in which relations between signs and their referents are conventionally established. Being properly trained therefore ensures that participants are prepared to unlock the meaning lodged in the messages. In Ernest Satow’s words, the production and maintenance of the diplomatic order rests with “diligently acquired knowledge and practical experience of the art,” which educate diplomats in the rituals’ rationale (Satow 1917, 52; Scheffler 1997, 160). The efficacy of diplomatic rituals depends, this is to say, not only on their fitting performance by diplomats, but also on the degree to which diplomats are socialized in the “appropriate

construction and interpretation of messages and behaviors” (Mitchell-Kernan 1972, 173).

This socialization is fundamental in another way. It is fundamental because, according to Catherine Bell, it facilitates the emergence of “ritualized body,” that is, a body invested with a “sense of ritual” (Bell 1992, 80). A ritual sense bears the marks of its semiotic environment and is a form of incorporated knowledge about what counts as ritual, on the one hand, and what is ritually acceptable, on the other (see Mälksoo 2021, 53–78; Ringmar 2016, 101–25). As such, a ritual sense can claim a reasonably close correspondence with Pierre Bourdieu’s habitus, without being reducible to it. In fact, for Bourdieu, a ritual “has meaning and interest only for someone who possesses the cultural competence, that is, the code, into which it is encoded. . . . A beholder who lacks the specific code feels lost in a chaos of sounds, rhythms, colors and lines, without rhyme and reason” (Bourdieu 1984, 2).

The diplomatic order is a culturally shaped field of sensory experience, wherein “bits of body,” says Margaret Wetherell, “get patterned together with feelings and thoughts, interaction patterns and relationships” (Wetherell 2012, 13–4). Every diplomatic order instantiates an “emotional community,” also called “affective community” to emphasize the collective aspect of the feeling (Rosenwein 2006; Hutchinson 2016, 106). As such the perdurance of a diplomatic order is an index of the perdurance of “fundamental assumptions, values, goals, feeling rules, and accepted modes of expression,” which bind participants to the diplomatic order (Rosenwein 2006, 24). That is, the stability of a diplomatic order rests on an “emotion norm,” of sorts (Koschut 2014; Rösch 2021). This account, which acknowledges the contribution of emotions to the creation and maintenance of a diplomatic order, does not claim to exhaust our understanding of the various perspectives on the relationship between emotions and rituals. But it emphasizes the importance of studying the sensory foundations of any diplomatic order (Wong 2016, 156–7; Solomon and Steele 2017, 276). Ritual sense is both experiential and conceptual, that is, it does not only provide diplomats with “knowledge about” but also with participatory knowledge (“knowledge by”) (Innis 2005, 210).

This raises the highly critical question of whether diplomatic order should be understood as a normative or as a descriptive concept. In fact, in my view, it is both. In the first place, diplomatic order refers to “relations between people who regard themselves as distinctive and separate from one another” (Sharp 2004, 361). The descriptive conclusion that follows is that diplomatic order embodies the ensemble of practices that mediate relations between agents of different walks of life who belong to the diplomatic realm. In the second plan, diplomatic order becomes normative where it is established as a measure of conventionally acceptable, expected mode of behavior and thus as a criterion of an appropriate engagement with one another in the diplomatic domain.

Conclusion

This paper has shown that we make a serious mistake when we construe ritual efficacy in either/or terms and, more fundamentally, when we lull ourselves in searching for a domain-invariant theory of ritual efficacy. In contrast, I have stated at the outset that our task is made more tractable when we examine efficacy in the domain in which the characteristics and arrangements of signs constitutive of a particular order make sense.

We can summarize the key features of our argument in the following terms. Scientific research seems to confirm that rit-

uals, beyond their semiotic function, have a formative effect on the participants; they can enact certain phenomena and put actors in motion. Scholars who subscribe to a performative approach assume that rituals are entrenched in a formal procedure or a system of rules in terms of which their efficacy is ascertained. However, the performative view, which permits rituals to escape the indictment for irrationality, also reduces efficacy to the fitness of the procedure and ignores what rituals accomplish. Performative is an important element of ritual, but it is not defining of it. Although we are only beginning to access the biological and cognitive circuits of ritual work, a growing body of evidence provides us with a record to supplement our efforts to understand how the “human brain and nervous system constrain, if not actually construct. . . ritualistic experience” (Grimes 2014, 309; Xygalatas 2022). In sum, diplomatic rituals, like any other ritual, rest on both cognitive and cultural activities, and ritual effects express privileged (learned) interactions between the two. Rituals rely on cultural vehicles such as words, songs, gestures or taste to transmit meaning to the brain, arouse emotional responses and elicit a behavioral sequence (Graybiel 2008, 371–2; Hüsken 2007b: 337–66). Hence, the informative account of ritual efficacy I have put forward in this paper.

Clearly, rituals have different socio-emotional significance and stimulate distinctive effects, depending upon the specific domain wherein they occur. The most important consequence of diplomatic rituals is the acceptance of the order diplomats contribute to. In order words, performance is acceptance. To emphasize acceptance is not to argue that insincerity and deceit of the performers are not important and should not be reckoned with. They certainly should. But the effective operation of a ritual does not require diplomats to necessarily align their inward state of mind with their participation in the performance of a ritual order. In short, while diplomatic performance “does not eliminate insincerity, it renders it publicly impotent. It is the visible, explicit, public act of acceptance, and not the invisible, ambiguous, private sentiment, which is socially and morally binding” (Rappaport 1999, 122). This does not mean that diplomats will conform to the moral obligation thus instantiated. Rather, it means that their participation establishes or reenacts the rules and norms which sustain a diplomatic order. Perhaps, then, the efficacy of diplomatic rituals lies less in what they induce in participants than in the mode of interactions they make (almost) unquestionable.

Acknowledgments

I am very grateful to Maria Mälksoo for her careful reading of different iterations of this article. Thanks to the journal coeditors and the two anonymous referees for their thoughtful engagement and suggestions, which have enabled me to strengthen this article. Finally, thanks to Brent J. Steele for his help throughout the resubmission process. The usual disclaimer applies.

Funding

The open access publication of the Special Forum this article is part of has been supported by the ERC Consolidator Grant RITUAL DETERRENCE, project number 101043468.

References

AALBERTS, TANJA et al. 2020. “Rituals of World Politics: on (Visual) Practices Disordering Things.” *Critical Studies on Security* 8: 240–64. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21624887.2020.1792734>.

- AALBERTS, TANJA, AND SOFIA STOLK. 2020. “the Peace Palace: Materializing a Home for the International Community.” *American Journal of International Law Unbound* 114: 117–22.
- AHERN, EMILY. 1979. “the Problem of Efficacy: Strong and Weak Illocutionary Acts.” *Man* 14: 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2801637>.
- AMBOS, CLAUS. 2007. “Types of Ritual Failure and Mistakes in Ritual in Cuneiform Sources.” In *When Rituals Go Wrong: Mistakes, Failure and the Dynamics of Ritual*, edited by U. Hüsken, 25–47. Leiden: Brill.
- ASAD, TALAL. 1993. *Genealogies of Religion: Discipline and Reasons of Power in Christianity and Islam*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press. <http://doi.org/10.1353/book.16014>.
- AUSTIN, JOHN R. 1962. *How to Do Things with Words*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- BAELE, STÉPHANE, AND THIERRY BALZACQ. 2022. “International Rituals: an Analytical Framework and Its Theoretical Repertoires.” *Review of International Studies* 48: 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0260210521000401>.
- BALZACQ, THIERRY. 2019. “Rituals and Diplomacy.” In *Global Diplomacy: An Introduction to Theory and Practice*, edited by Frédéric Ramel, Frédéric Charillon and Frédéric Ramel. 111–122. Palgrave Macmillan.
- BASSO, KEITH. 1996. *Wisdom Sits in Places: Landscape and Language among the Western Apache*. Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press.
- BATESON, GREGORY. 1972. *Steps to an Ecology of Mind*. New York: Ballantine.
- BELL, CATHERINE. 1992. *Ritual Theory, Ritual Practice*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- BOURDIEU, PIERRE. 1984. *Distinction: a Social Critique of the Judgement of Taste*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- BOUSSAGUET, LAURIE, AND FLORENCE FAUCHER. 2024. *Symbolic Policy*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009290975>.
- BULL, HEDLEY. 2002. *The Anarchical Society: a Study of Order in World Politics*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- CAMPBELL, JOSEPH. 1959. *The Mask of God, Vol. 1: Primitive Mythology*. New York: The Viking Press.
- CHAMBON, ALBERT. 1983. *Mais Que Font Donc Ces Diplomates Entre Deux Cocktails?* Paris: A. Pedone.
- CHURCHLAND, PAUL M. 2005. “Functionalism at Forty: a Critical Retrospective.” *Journal of Philosophy* 102: 33–50. <https://doi.org/10.5840/jp-hil2005102136>.
- COHEN, RAYMOND. 2001. “the Great Tradition: the Spread of Diplomacy in the Ancient World.” *Diplomacy & Statecraft* 12: 23–38. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09592290108406186>.
- COLLINS, RANDALL. 2005. *Interaction Ritual Chains*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- CORNUT, JÉRÉMIE. 2018. “Diplomacy, Agency, and the Logic of Improvisation and Virtuosity in Practice.” *European Journal of International Relations* 24: 712–36. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354066117725156>.
- CROSSLEY, NICK. 2011. *Towards Relational Sociology*. London: Routledge.
- DELEUZE, GILLES, AND FELIX GUATTARI. 1988. *A Thousand Plateaus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia*, trans. by B. Massumi. London: Athlone Press, 1988.
- DINZELBACHER, PETER. 2010. “Healing Rituals in the Medieval West.” In *The Problem of Ritual Efficacy*, edited by Sax et al., 67–92. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195394405.001.0001>.
- DOLCOS, SANDRA et al. 2012. “the Power of a Handshake: Neural Correlates of Evaluative Judgments in Observed Social Interactions.” *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience* 24: 2292–305. https://doi.org/10.1162/jocn_a_00295.
- DRIVER, TOM F. 1998. *Liberating Rites: Understanding the Transformative Power of Ritual*. Boulder, CO: Westview.
- DURKHEIM, EMILE. 1965. *The Elementary Forms of Religious Life*. New York: Free Press.
- ERICKSON, ERICK. 1966. “Ontogeny of Ritualization in Man.” In A Discussion of the Ritualization of Behavior in Animals and Man, convened by J. Huxley. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B. Biological Sciences* 251: 337–49.
- EVANS-PRITCHARD, EDWARD E. 1937. *Witchcraft: Oracles and Magic among the Azande*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- FIERKE, KARIN M. 2013. *Political Self-Sacrifice: Agency, Body and Emotion in International Relations*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- FRAZER, JAMES. 1963. *The Golden Bough: a Study in Magic and Religion*. New York: Macmillan & CO.

- GARDINER, D. S. 1983. "Performativity in Ritual: the Mianmin Case." *Man* 18: 346–60. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2801439>.
- GOFFMAN, ERVING. 1967. *Interaction Ritual*. Garden City, NJ: Doubleday.
- GOFFMAN, ERVING. 1974. *Frame Analysis: an Essay on the Organization of Experience*. New York: Harper and Row.
- GRAYBIEL, ANN M. 2008. "Habits, Rituals, and the Evaluative Brain." *Annual Review of Neuroscience* 31: 359–87. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.neuro.29.051605.112851>.
- GRIMES, RONALD L. 1990. *Ritual Criticism: Case Studies in Its Practice, Essays in Its Theory*. Columbia: University of South Carolina Press.
- GRIMES, RONALD L. 2011. "Ritual, Media, and Conflict: an Introduction." In *Ritual, Media, and Conflict*, edited by R. L. Grimes et al., 1–34. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199735235.001.0001>.
- GRIMES, RONALD L. 2014. *The Craft of Ritual Studies*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- HOLLIS, MARTIN. 1968. "Reason and Ritual." *Philosophy* 43: 231–47. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0031819100009207>.
- HOMANS, GEORGE C. 1941. "Anxiety and Ritual: the Theories of Malinowski and Radcliffe-Brown." *American Anthropologist* 43: 164–72. <https://doi.org/10.1525/aa.1941.43.2.02a00020>.
- HUMPHREY, CAROLINE, AND JAMES LAIDLAW. 1994. *The Archetypal Actions of Ritual*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198277880.001.0001>.
- HÜSKEN, UTE. 2007a. "Mistakes, Procedural Errors and Incorrect Performances." In *When Rituals Go Wrong: Mistakes, Failure and the Dynamics of Ritual*, edited by U. Hüskén, 21–3. Leiden: Brill.
- HÜSKEN, UTE. 2007b. "Ritual Dynamics and Ritual Failure." In *When Rituals Go Wrong: Mistakes, Failure and the Dynamics of Ritual*, edited by U. Hüskén, 337–66. Leiden: Brill.
- HUTCHISON, EMMA. 2016. *Affective Communities in World Politics*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781316154670>.
- INNIS, ALBERT. 2005. "The Tactic Logic of Ritual Embodiments: Rappaport and Polanyi between Thick and Thin." In *Ritual in Its Own Right: Exploring the Dynamics of Transformation*, edited by Don Handelman and Galina Lindquist, 197–212. New York: Berghahn Books.
- KAPFERER, BRUCE. 1983. *A Celebration of Demons: Exorcism and the Aesthetics of Healing in Sri Lanka*. Bloomington, IN: Indiana University Press.
- KECK, FRÉDÉRIC. 2012. "Goffman, Durkheim et Les Rites De la Vie Quotidienne." *Archives de philosophie* 75: 471–92. <https://doi.org/10.3917/aphi.75.0471>.
- KERTZER, DAVID. 1988. *Ritual Politics and Power*. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- KINCAID, HAROLD. 1990. "Assessing Functional Explanations in the Social Sciences." *PSA: Proceedings of the Biennial Meeting of the Philosophy of Science Association* 2: 341–54.
- KNOTTER, LUCAS. 2020. "Why Declare Independence? Observing, Believing, and Performing the Ritual." *Review of International Studies* 47: 252–71. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0260210520000443>.
- KOSCHUT, SIMON. 2014. "Emotional (Security) Communities: the Significance of Emotion Norms in Inter-Allied Conflict Management." *Review of International Studies* 40: 533–58. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0260210513000375>.
- KOSCHUT, SIMON. 2023. "when International Rituals Go Wrong: How Ritual Failure Undermines Peaceful Change in NATO." *Cooperation and Conflict* 59: 290–307. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00108367231184731>.
- KUSTERMANS, JORG et al. 2022. "Ritual and Authority in World Politics." *Cambridge Review of International Affairs* 35: 2–30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/095557571.2021.1975647>.
- LAFONT, BERTRAND. 2001. "International Relations in the Ancient Near East: the Birth of a Complete Diplomatic System." *Diplomacy and Statecraft* 12: 39–60. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09592290108406187>.
- LANGER, ROBERT et al. 2010. "Ritual as Source of Conflict." In *Ritual Media, and Conflict*, edited by R. L. Grimes et al., 93–132. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- LEACH, EDMUND R. 1954. *Political Systems of Highland Burma: a Study of Kachin Social Structure*. Boston: Beacon Press.
- LEACH, EDMUND R. 1964. "Ritual." In *A Dictionary of the Social Sciences*, edited by J. Gould and W. Kolk, 607. London: Tavistock.
- LUKES, STEVEN. 1975. "Political Ritual and Social Integration." *Sociology* 9: 289–308. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003803857500902005>.
- MÄLKSOO, MARIA. 2021. "a Ritual Approach to Deterrence: I am, Therefore I Deter." *European Journal of International Relations* 27: 53–78. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354066120966039>.
- MARSDEN, PETER V. 2015. "Social Order from the Bottom Up?" In *Order on the Edge of Chaos: Social Psychology and the Problem of Social Order*, edited by E. J. Lawler, S. R. Thye and J. Yoon, 309–22. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139924627>.
- MAUSS, MARCEL. 2007. *Essai sur le Don. Forme et Raison de L'échange dans les Sociétés Archaiques*. Paris: Presses universitaires de France.
- MCCONNELL, FIONA. 2018. "Performing Diplomatic Decorum: Repertoires of 'Appropriate' Behavior in the Margins of International Diplomacy." *International Political Sociology* 12: 362–81. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ips/oly021>.
- MERTON, ROBERT K. 1968. "Manifest and Latent Functions." In *Social Theory and Social Structure*, 73–138. New York: Free Press.
- MITCHELL-KERNAN, CLAUDIA. 1972. "Signifying and Marking: Two Afro-American Speech Acts." In *Directions in Sociolinguistics: the Ethnography of Communication*, edited by J. Gumperz and D. H. Hymes, 161–79. Holt: Rinehart and Winston.
- MITZEN, JENNIFER. 2006. "Ontological Security in World Politics: State Identity and the Security Dilemma." *European Journal of International Relations* 12: 341–70. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354066106067346>.
- MITZEN, JENNIFER. 2015. "from Representation to Governing: Diplomacy and the Constitution of International Public Order." In *Diplomacy and the Making of World Politics*, edited by O. J. Sending, V. Pouliot and I. B. Neumann, 111–39. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781316162903>.
- MOORE, SALLY F. 1977. "Political Meetings and the Simulation of Unanimity: Kilimanjaro." In *Secular Ritual*, edited by S. F. Moore and B. Myerhoff, 151–72. Amsterdam: Van Gorcum.
- MURDOCH, IRIS. 1970. *The Sovereignty of Good*. London: Routledge.
- NAIR, DEEPAK. 2020. "Sociability in International Politics: Golf and ASEAN's Cold War Diplomacy." *International Political Sociology* 14: 196–214. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ips/olz024>.
- NEUMANN, IVER B. 2012. *At Home with the Diplomats: inside a European Foreign Ministry*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press. <https://doi.org/10.7591/cornell/9780801449932.001.0001>.
- OPONDO, SAM O. 2010. "Decolonizing Diplomacy: Reflections on African Estrangement and Exclusion." In *Sustainable Diplomacies*, edited by C. Constantinou and J. Der Derian, 109–27. Basingstoke, UK: Palgrave Macmillan. <https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230297159>.
- PILE, STEVE. 2010. "Emotions and Affect in Recent Human Geography." *Transactions* 35: 5–20.
- POLANYI, MICHAEL. 1958. *Personal Knowledge: towards a Post-Critical Philosophy*. London: Routledge.
- POST, EMILY. 1940. *Etiquette: the Blue Book of Social Usage*. New York, NY: Funk & Wagnall.
- QUACK, JOHANNES, AND PAUL TÖBELMANN. 2010. "Questioning 'Ritual Efficacy.'" *Journal of Ritual Studies* 24: 13–28.
- QUACK, JOHANNES. 2010. "Bell, Bourdieu, and Wittgenstein on Ritual Sense." In *The Problem of Ritual Efficacy*, edited by W. S. Sax, J. Quack and J. Weinhold, 169–88. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195394405.001.0001>.
- RADCLIFFE-BROWN, A. R. 1952. *Structure and Function in Primitive Society*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul.
- RADCLIFFE-BROWN, A. R. 1965. "Religion and Society." in *Structure and Function in Primitive Society: Essays and Addresses*. New York: Free Press, 1965.
- RAPPAPORT, ROY. 1999. *Ritual and Religion in the Making of Humanity*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- RINGMAR, ERIK. 2012. "Performing International System: the East-Asian, Alternatives to the Westphalian Order." *International Organization* 66: 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0020818312000033>.
- RINGMAR, ERIK. 2016. "How the World Stage Makes Its Subjects: an Embodied Critique of Constructivist IR Theory." *Journal of International Relations and Development* 19: 101–25. <https://doi.org/10.1057/jird.2015.33>.
- RÖSCH, FELIX. 2021. "Affect, Practice, and Change: Dancing World Politics at the Congress of Vienna." *Cooperation and Conflict* 56: 123–40.
- ROSENWEIN, BARBARA H. 2006. *Emotional Communities in the Early Middle Ages*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.
- SATOW, ERNEST. 1917. *A Guide to Diplomatic Practice*. London: Longmans, Green & Company.

- SAX, WILLIAM. 2010. "Ritual and the Problem of Efficacy." In *The Problem of Ritual Efficacy*, edited by W. S. Sax, J. Quack and J. Weinhold, 3–16, Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195394405.001.0001>.
- SCHEFFLER, ISRAEL. 1997. *Symbolic Worlds*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- SCHIFFRIN, DEBORAH. 1998. "Handwork as Ceremony: the Case of the Handshake." *Semiotica* 12: 189–202.
- SEARLE, JOHN R. 1969. *Speech Acts*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139173438>.
- SEARLE, JOHN R. 1983. *Intentionality: an Essay in the Philosophy of Mind*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139173452>.
- SHARP, PAUL. 2004. "The Idea of Diplomatic Culture and Its Sources." *Malta: DiploFoundation: In Intercultural Communication and Diplomacy*, edited by Hannah Slavik, 361–379.
- SHILS, EDWARD, AND MICHAEL YOUNG. 1953. "the Meaning of the Coronation." *The Sociological Review* 1: 63–81. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-954X.1953.tb00953.x>.
- SKINNER, QUENTIN. 1969. "Meaning and Understanding in the History of Ideas." *History and Theory* 8: 3–53. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2504188>.
- SMITH, WILFRED C. 1991. *The Meaning and End of Religion: a New Approach to the Religious Traditions of Mankind*. New York: Macmillan.
- SOFER, SASSON. 2007. "the Diplomatic Corps as a Symbol of Diplomatic Culture." In *The Diplomatic Corps as an Institution of International Society*, edited by P. Sharp and G. Wiseman 31–8. Basingstoke, UK: Palgrave.
- SOLOMON, TY, AND BRENT J. STEELE. 2017. "Micro-moves in International Relations Theory." *European Journal of International Relations* 23: 267–91. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354066116634442>.
- SOLOMON, TY. 2019. "Rhythm and Mobilization in International Relations." *International Studies Quarterly* 63: 1001–13. <https://doi.org/10.1093/isq/sqz074>.
- SOLOMON, TY. 2023. "Up in the Air: Ritualized Atmosphere and the Global Black Lives Matter Movement." *European Journal of International Relations* 29: 576–601. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13540661231181989>.
- SORENSEN, JORGEN P. 2006. "Efficacy." In *Theorizing Rituals: Issues, Topics, Approaches, Concepts*, edited by J. Kreinath, J. Snoek and M. Stausberg, 523–31. Leiden: Brill. <https://doi.org/10.1163/9789047410775>.
- STAAL, FRITS. 1990. *Ritual and Mantras: Rules without Meaning*. New Delhi: Jainendra Prakash at Shri Jainendra Press.
- STEELE, BRENT J. 2008. *Ontological Security in International Relations: Self-Identity and the IR State*. London: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203018200>.
- STEWART, PAMELA J., AND STRATHERN ANDREW. 2014. "Ritual: Key Concepts in Religion." *London: Bloomsbury*.
- TAMBIAH, STANLEY. 1985. *Culture, Thought and Action: an Anthropological Perspective*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.4159/harvard.9780674433748>.
- TURNER, VICTOR. 1967. *The Forest of Symbols: Aspects of Ndembu Ritual*. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press.
- WEGNER, NICOLE. 2021. "Rituals, Rhythms, and the Discomforting Endurance of Militarism: Affective Methodologies and Ethico-Political Challenges." *Global Studies Quarterly* 1: 1–10.
- WETHERELL, MARGARET. 2012. *Affect and Emotion: a New Social Science Understanding*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446250945>.
- WITTGENSTEIN, LUDWIG. 1993. "Remarks on Frazer's *Golden Bough* (1931–1948)." In *Philosophical Occasions*, edited by J. Klagge and A. Nordmann, 115–55. Indianapolis: Hackett, 1993.
- WONG, SEANON S. 2016. "Emotions and the Communication of Intentions in Face-to-Face Diplomacy." *European Journal of International Relations* 22: 144–67. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354066115581059>.
- XYGALATAS, DIMITRIS. 2022. *Ritual: How Seemingly Senseless Acts Make Life Worth Living*. New York: Little Brown Spark.